

Time-resolved Studies of Magnetic Field Effect on 9-Cyanophenanthrene – *trans*-anethole Exciplex Luminescence

SAMITA BASU, TAPAS CHAKRABORTY and MIHIR CHOWDHURY*

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

Nanosecond time-resolved studies of magnetic effect on 9-cyanophenanthrene-*trans*-anethole exciplex luminescence have been carried out with the help of time-correlated-single-photon-counting technique. This is the first report of its kind with free donor-acceptor system and has been possible because of proper choice of solvent. An analytical model has been suggested to interpret the results.

It is now well established that hyperfine interaction mechanism is responsible for the magnetic-field-dependent fast singlet-triplet conversion in radical ion pairs (RIP)¹⁻¹⁴. In brief, singlet RIPs initially formed through electron transfer from donor to acceptor molecule in moderately polar medium diffuse apart and undergo either short-time (e.g. nanosecond) geminate or long-time (e.g. microsecond) homogeneous recombinations. During the diffusional excursion process when the RIP separates to a distance where exchange interaction energy (J) becomes negligible, nuclear magnetic moments which are coupled to the unpaired electrons by hyperfine interaction (HFI) may induce a transition in the RIP from the singlet (S) to the triplet (T) state. The external applied magnetic field competes with the internal HFI field and if large enough reduces the RIP's S-T transition rate to one-third of its zero-field value as the components of the triplet surface split, due to Zeeman interaction, into T_+ , T_0 and T_- levels. This causes an increase in steady-state population of the singlet RIP which in turn causes an increase in the population of geminately recombined luminescent contact ion pair (CIP) and thus enhances exciplex luminescence intensity. It is clear that the geminately recombined CIP concentration as well as the magnetic-field-induced change should be time-dependent. Homogeneous recombination process may or may not be magnetic field dependent¹⁵⁻¹⁷, but it does not come into the picture during the short nanosecond lifetime of the exciplex.

Magnetic field effect on steady-state luminescence of following exciplexes, linked and unlinked, have been studied: pyrene-diethylaniline (Py-DEA)⁷, pyrene-dimethylaniline (Py-DMA)⁸⁻¹⁰, 9-cyanophenanthrene-*trans*-anethole (CNP-AN)¹¹, Py-(CH₂)_n-DMA (n varying from 2 to 16)¹², α -(4-dimethylaminophenyl)- ω -(9-phenanthryl) (Ph-(CH₂)_n-DMA) (n varying from 2 to 10)¹³ and Py-(CH₂)_n-COO-CH₂-CH₂-polystyrene-CH(CH₂)DMA¹⁴. Time-resolved studies on magnetic field have been

successfully attempted on the population of the secondary species, e.g. free ions or acceptor triplet, through delayed fluorescence^{2,8} or flash photolysis technique^{1,4-6}. It is of interest to analyse the geminate recombination rate directly as a function of time through monitoring of exciplex luminescence as this should allow shorter time resolution. Brocklehurst¹⁸ studied time-dependence of magnetic field effect on ion pairs generated from hydrocarbon in non-polar solvent in nanosecond scale by pulse radiolysis technique. Weller *et al.*¹² have recently performed time-resolved studies on exciplex luminescence in chained system. Though the spatial diffusion in the free acceptor/donor systems should be easier to be treated as a model, yet no one, as far as we are aware, has reported the magnetic field effect on free or unlinked acceptor/donor system as a function of time, presumably because of the limitation in signal-to-noise ratio of the time-resolved technique. Recently, we have reported that the percentage magnetic field effect in steady-state luminescence can be increased considerably by appropriate choice of solvent^{14,19-21}. This increase in the magnitude of the effect has helped us to time-resolve the phenomenon. Two different types of exciplexes, e.g. Py-DMA (typical heteroexcimer^{11,22}) and CNP-AN (mixed excimeric type¹¹) have been studied by us. Here, we report the results of time-resolved studies on CNP-AN exciplex and our attempt to interpret the results in terms of a schematic analytical model.

Experimental

The experimental set-up for measurement of magnetic field modulated luminescence ($\Delta\phi$) was described earlier in detail⁹. Time-resolved studies were done with the help of a nanosecond fluorimeter (Applied Photophysics) based on time-correlated single-photon-counting technique. A magnetic field was generated by an electromagnet placed directly inside the sample chamber of the

spectrophotometer. The absence of any possible spurious effect on photomultiplier output was carefully tested with pyrene excimer luminescence which should be insensitive to magnetic field. The photomultiplier was cooled to get rid of high dark counts. Quantum counter (where intensity \times time remains constant) was used to avoid any fluctuation of lamp intensity.

The experiment was carried out in a solvent mixture of tetrahydrofuran (THF) and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) having a dielectric constant $\epsilon \approx 16$. The percentage change of luminescence of magnetic field ($\Delta\phi/\phi\%$) is maximum ($\approx 4.5\%$) at this ϵ -value and this permits greater signal-to-noise ratio for the time-resolved magnetic field studies.

9-Cyanophenanthrene (CNP) and *trans*-anethole (AN) (Aldrich; 99% pure) were used as such. Spectroscopic grade THF and DMF solvents were dried and distilled properly. The concentrations of CNP and AN were 10^{-5} and 8×10^{-5} M respectively. All the samples were degassed by passing N_2 for 40 min; it was ensured that no degradation of the sample took place during the experiment. A saturating magnetic field (200 Gauss¹¹) was applied when needed, during the experiment.

Results and Discussion

A casual look at the single-photon-counting histograms (Fig. 1) of the exciplex luminescence in absence and in presence of magnetic field (200 Gauss) might give the impression that the magnetic field effect on the singlet luminescence is a slow process which is operative only at the later phase of the decay. However, this apparent slowness is

Fig. 1.

only a reflection of the exponential nature of the decay which makes the percent enhancement of luminescence more prominent at later times and

this may be fruitfully utilised for the magnetic field study itself by use of a time window at an appropriate time. The decay curve consists of a growth part followed by an exponential decay. At longer times both curves deviate from single-exponential behaviour. It has been found that the initial decay time increases from 6.5 ns (τ_{1D}) to 6.8 ns (τ_{2D}) on application of a saturating magnetic field. The percentage increase in lifetime tallys well with the percentage increase of integrated luminescence.

The basic difficulty in modelling the magnetic-field-induced recombination process is our lack of knowledge of a number of essential parameters. For example, we have very little information on the potential energy surface, particularly at short inter-radical distances. Similarly, there is little knowledge either of the distance (or distances) at which RIPs are formed from neutral excited species or of the distance at which RIPs recombine to form luminescent exciplex. However, in spite of uncertainties and gaps in our knowledge of essential parameters, we have tried to formulate a schematic analytic model to provide a framework for discussion of our results. The details of our model, and the criticisms and justifications of our assumptions have been discussed previously^{11,14,22,25}. Here, we summarise the model, the basic assumptions and the results specifically in relation to temporal variation. Following are the important points to be noted.

(i) In moderately polar solvent, the solvent-shared-ion-pairs (SSIP) are formed first at an intermediate distance r_g . A fraction of SSIP may form CIP at a distance R crossing a potential energy barrier in the potential energy curve between SSIP and CIP states, which signifies that once the RIP crosses the activation barrier, i.e. approaches closer to a specific distance R , the probability of forming the luminescent exciplex increases considerably. However, the exciplex state can leak through the activation barrier and appear again as SSIP. (ii) The diffusion is continuous and a Coulombic force field is assumed. (iii) It has been mentioned earlier that RIP undergoes ISC process when the distance between the partners is sufficient to ignore J . But here, for retaining the simplicity of the model it is assumed that $J=0$ over the domain of spatial diffusion. (iv) The diffusion process and the spin-rephasing dynamics are decoupled. The ISC process can be treated phenomenologically as a leakage to the triplet surface. (v) All encounters are assumed as geminate encounters. (vi) Exciplex can be formed from only singlet RIP and $\rho_s = 1 - \rho_T$, where, ρ_s and ρ_T are the singlet and triplet densities respectively. We assume,

$$\rho_T = At \quad \text{for } t \leq t'$$

$$\text{and } \rho_s = A_{\text{int}} t' \quad \text{for } t > t'$$

where, A is the HFI induced ISC rate in absence of magnetic field. This is in accord with the calculation of Werner *et al.*¹⁶ for Py-DMA system.

The small oscillations in ρ_T versus time curve of reference (16, 17) are supposed to be washed off by lack of coherence and neglected in our model.

The spin-independent time-dependent recombination rate has been obtained by Hong and Noolandi by solving Smoluchowski equation in the long time limit²², i.e. when $Dt > r_g^2, r_c^2$, where D is the mutual diffusivity of RIP and r_c is the Onsager radius which is equal to $e^2/\epsilon kT$, k is the Boltzman constant²³, and given by the expression²²,

$$K(t) = \left[\frac{r_c}{(4\pi D)^{1/2}} \frac{U(r_g)}{|U(\alpha)|^2} t^{-3/2} \right],$$

where, $U(r) = e^{-r_c/r} + \left[\frac{D r_c}{h R^2} - 1 \right] e^{-r_c/R}$, $h = \mathcal{H} U_0/4$.

Here, U_0 is an effective velocity of crossing the potential barrier between SSIP and CIP at the reaction radius and \mathcal{H} is a transmission coefficient. So h is the effective parameter which governs the efficiency of luminescent exciplex formation through $SSIP \rightleftharpoons CIP$ conversion.

Considering both the spin rephasing and spatial dynamics and recombination together, the rate of exciplex formation in absence of external magnetic field is given by

$$(1 - At) K(t), \quad \text{when } t \leq t'$$

$$\text{and } (1 - A_{sat}) K(t), \quad \text{when } t > t'$$

The differential equation for the concentration c of luminescent CIP can be written as

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = -k_1(c) + K(t) (1 - At) \quad \text{for } t \leq t'$$

$$= -k_1(c) + K(t) (1 - A_{sat}) \quad \text{for } t > t'$$

the first term taking account the decay of the luminescent exciplex (CIP) by radiative and non-radiative channels, so that k_1 can be written as τ_1^{-1} . In the presence of a saturating magnetic field $S \rightarrow T_{\pm}$ channels are blocked and ISC rate reduces to $A/3$ ¹⁶. So, a similar equation can be written down with A replaced by $A/3$ for saturating field and it can be easily derived that the magnetic-field-induced change,

$$\Delta c(t) = \frac{2}{3} AP e^{-k_1 t} \int_0^{t'} t^{-1/2} e^{-k_1 t} dt +$$

$$\frac{2}{3} AP t' e^{-k_1 t} \int_{t'}^t t^{-3/2} e^{-k_1 t} dt,$$

where, P stands for $\frac{r_c}{(4\pi D)^{1/2}} \frac{U(r_g)}{|U(\alpha)|^2}$.

The $\Delta c(t)$, of course, needs to be convoluted with exciting light pulse $L(t)$ with proper shift δ , according to the following expression,

$$\Delta c(t)_{\text{convoluted}} = \int_0^{t+\delta} L(X) \Delta c(t+\delta-X) dx$$

²²For justification of long-time limit expression and use of single parameter t' , see Refs. 22 and 25.

before a comparison can be made with the experimental data. Fig. 2 compares the experimental curve, where the differences between counts (ΔZ) in presence and in absence of magnetic field is plotted against time. The theoretical convoluted $\Delta c(t)$ versus t plot assumes $k_1 = \tau_1^{-1}$ and $t' \approx 12$ ns and a fairly good agreement between two curves can be achieved. It may be pointed out that the analytical model is very simple and straightforward one, and the time-variation depends on only one adjustable parameter, t'^* . The variable parameters r_g, r_c, D etc., except t' , do not matter and may be taken as arbitrary. The value of the adjustable parameter t' which fits the experimental curve is same as that in Py-DMA system²² and is also very close to the value obtained by Schulten's calculation¹⁶.

Fig. 2

Acknowledgement

The work has been carried out under a joint Indo-US project (CE-2) sponsored by the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India and the National Institute of Standards and Technology, U.S.A. The authors thank Dr. D. N. Nath for discussion of the theoretical model and experimental assistance, and Dr. S. C. Bera, T. Kundu and R. Dutta for help with data transfer and manipulation.

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